

THE EXISTENCE OF CUSTOMARY LAW COMMUNITIES IN INDONESIA'S POSITIVE LEGAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the fact that social changes resulting from modernization and globalization present particular challenges to maintaining indigenous communities. This has resulted in social disintegration and the loss of their cultural identity. This research aims to answer questions regarding the nature of the existence of customary law communities, the regulation of the existence of customary law communities in the positive legal system and to find the role of the state in protecting the existence of customary law communities in Indonesia. This research is a normative legal research using the Philosophical Approach, the Statute Approach, the Conceptual Approach, and the Historical Approach. The results of the study indicate that customary law communities are not merely traditional communities, but are collective legal subjects that have their own government systems, customary territories, and dispute resolution mechanisms that operate effectively within their communities. Regulations regarding customary law communities are not only contained in the constitution, but also in various sectoral laws and regulations. The ideal role of the state does not merely stop at normative recognition, but must be translated into concrete policies that guarantee rights to customary land, local wisdom, access to natural resources, and the political participation of customary communities in decision-making processes that affect their lives. The recommendations that can be given generally emphasize that regulating the existence of customary law communities in the positive legal system in Indonesia requires a holistic, progressive, and social justice-based approach.

Keywords: Customary Law, Customary Law Communities.

INTRODUCTION

The existence of Customary Law Communities (MHA) is rooted in the nature of humans as social beings who inherently form communities and require a legal order to achieve order. As Cicero's adage, "Ubi societas ibi ius" which means "where there is society, there is law" thus reflecting that law is a necessity in community life. self-regulating communities) with their own social, political, and legal systems, and have strong ties to their land and natural resources. Customary law communities are autonomous in regulating their life systems, both legal, political, economic, and so on, born and developed together, and maintained by the community itself. (Hadikusuma, 1983) Understanding Indigenous Law Communities (ILM) is inseparable from the concept of Indigenous Peoples in general. This is because Indigenous Law Communities are essentially an elaboration or further elaboration of the concept of Indigenous Peoples.

Conceptually, the position of MHA within the national legal system can be analyzed through two main theoretical frameworks. First, the Theory of Legal Pluralism, which opposes the legal centralist view that only state law is valid. This theory recognizes the co-existence of various legal systems, including customary law, religious law, and state law, within a single social

space. In Indonesia's multicultural context, the existence of customary law, which regulates various aspects of community life, is a concrete manifestation of legal pluralism. Second, the Theory of Recognition, which emphasizes the crucial importance of state recognition, both de jure (through legislation) and de facto (in social practice), of the existence and rights of MHA. (Pudjilianto and Handayani 2022) Without explicit recognition, MHA are vulnerable to marginalization and the deprivation of their traditional rights.

In some customary law literature, the main focus is on the discussion of "Indigenous Communities," which in Dutch terminology is known as *rechtsgemeenschap*. Dutch customary law scholars, such as Cornelis Van Vollenhoven, define an indigenous community as a *volksgemeen-scappen* with its own social system, a strong connection to the land, management of its natural resources, and the freedom to maintain local values or local wisdom. (Sapromo, 2010) According to Bernard Ter Haar, he consistently uses the term *rechtsgemeenschap* to refer to this social entity. The word *Gemeenschap* itself can be defined as a community or association whose members are bound by a shared identity, close relationships, and collective responsibility. (Silubun and others 2022)

Although recognition of MHA is constitutionally guaranteed in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, its implementation faces serious legal problems. The main problem is the absence of a comprehensive umbrella law, resulting in partial and unsynchronized recognition of MHA across various sectoral laws, such as the Forestry Law and the Village Law. Furthermore, this recognition is often conditional and formalistic, as the existence of MHA is dependent on the establishment of regional regulations (*Perda*). (Widowati, Luthfi, and Guntur 2014) This administrative dependency creates legal uncertainty, with de facto surviving MHA being de jure recognized due to the lack of regional regulations. This situation was exacerbated by the enactment of Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation, which is considered to weaken the legal standing of MHA by simplifying business licensing in customary areas without adequate consultation mechanisms.

Philosophically, the existence of customary law communities also serves as a means of preserving cultural values and local wisdom. Customary law communities regulate not only relationships between people but also relationships with nature and the environment. This aligns with Fritjof Capra's view, which emphasizes that traditional ecological wisdom is often wiser in maintaining the balance of nature than modern approaches that tend to be exploitative. (Ismi, 2012) Therefore, the existence of indigenous legal communities is crucial to ensure they can continue to exist and contribute to the government system without losing their cultural identity. This must be based on the principle of respecting the rights of indigenous legal communities and protecting their local wisdom. The state must act as a facilitator, providing support and protection so that indigenous legal communities can function effectively in modern society.

Legal associations are the material foundation for the rights of indigenous peoples. This means that these rights are inherent in the association of indigenous peoples as legal subjects, and not simply based on cultural, subcultural, or ethnic groupings, as is often misunderstood. Full recognition of indigenous peoples as legal subjects will result in more appropriate policies

governing their rights related to natural resource management. As explained above, indigenous (legal) communities have two main characteristics. First, their existence predates the state. Because they emerged before the state was formed, the formation of indigenous peoples occurred naturally through political and social processes. Second, they are self-regulating communities and are thus capable of governing themselves.

Theoretically, the theory of Legal Pluralism is a concept that recognizes the existence of more than one legal system that applies simultaneously in a certain social or geographical area. (Tamanaha, 2021) This theory challenges the legal centralist view, which holds that only state law (positive law created and enforced by the state) is valid and applicable. In the context of legal pluralism, state law is only one of various legal systems that exist and interact within society. The existence of other legal systems, such as customary law, religious law, and customary law, is recognized as part of the legal reality.

This must be based on the principle of respecting the rights of indigenous peoples and protecting their local wisdom. The state must act as a facilitator, providing support and protection so that indigenous peoples can function effectively in modern society. Legal associations are the material foundation for indigenous peoples' rights. This means that these rights are inherent in indigenous peoples' associations as legal subjects, and not simply grouped based on culture, subculture, or ethnicity, as is often misunderstood. Full recognition of indigenous peoples as legal subjects will result in more appropriate policies governing their rights related to natural resource management.

As explained above, customary (legal) communities have two main characteristics. First, their existence predates that of the state. Because they emerged before the state was formed, the formation of customary legal communities occurred naturally through political and social processes. Second, they are self-regulating communities and are thus capable of governing themselves. Theoretically, the theory of Legal Pluralism is a concept that recognizes the existence of more than one legal system that applies simultaneously within a particular social or geographic area. This theory opposes the legal centralism view, which assumes that only state law (positive law created and enforced by the state) is valid and applicable. In the context of legal pluralism, state law is only one of various legal systems that exist and interact within society. The existence of other legal systems, such as customary law, religious law, and customary law, is recognized as part of the legal reality.

In the Indonesian context, legal pluralism is highly relevant because Indonesia is a multicultural country with hundreds of ethnic groups and diverse customs. The existence of Indigenous Peoples with their respective customary legal systems is a manifestation of legal pluralism in Indonesia. Customary law regulates various aspects of life within these communities, from marriage and inheritance to land ownership and dispute resolution. (Ismi, 2012).

Recognition of legal pluralism in Indonesia is constitutionally guaranteed in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, which recognizes and respects customary law communities and their traditional rights. (Government of the Republic of Indonesia, 2004).

Legal Problems of Customary Law Communities (MHA) have been explicitly recognized in the Indonesian constitution, specifically in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, which states that "The State recognizes and respects customary law communities and their traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia." However, this recognition is declarative and still leaves a number of serious legal problems in its implementation. One of the main problems is the absence of a Special Law that comprehensively regulates customary law communities. Until now, recognition of customary law communities is spread across various sectoral laws that are not in sync with each other, such as Law No. 5 of 1960 concerning Basic Agrarian Principles (UUPA), Law No. 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry, and Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages. (Ismi 2012).

Recognition of indigenous peoples (MHA) in various laws and regulations is often conditional and formalistic. One form of such recognition is stipulated in Article 67 of the Forestry Law, which states that indigenous communities are recognized only to the extent that they are recognized by the regional government through regional regulations. A similar provision is also stipulated in Article 97 of the Village Law, which states that customary villages are recognized after being established through regional regulations. This provision makes the existence of indigenous communities administratively dependent on regional government policy, even though many regions lack the legal framework or political will to issue regional regulations. As a result, the existence of indigenous communities is "de jure unrecognized" even though they "de facto still exist" and practice their own customary legal systems. This presents a legal problem because their legal status is unclear under national law, making it difficult for them to assert their rights to land, forests, or other resources.

Furthermore, the disharmony between laws and regulations also gives rise to overlapping authority and conflicting norms. For example, in Constitutional Court Decision No. 35/PUU-X/2012, the Court stated that "customary forests are no longer part of state forests." However, the implementation of this decision remains weak due to the lack of administrative recognition and derivative legislation. Even Law No. 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation contains numerous provisions that facilitate the granting of business permits in customary areas without consulting local communities, thereby weakening the legal position of indigenous communities within the national legal system.

The provisions in the Forestry and Land Cluster of Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation have sparked serious debate regarding the existence and protection of Indigenous Communities (MHA). This regulation significantly amends several key articles in Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry, particularly Articles 29 and 50, which were amended by Articles 36 and 37 of the Job Creation Law. (Government of the Republic of Indonesia, 2004) These changes are intended to expedite the business licensing process in forest areas and simplify administrative procedures, including eliminating or weakening the requirement to consult with directly affected communities, such as indigenous communities. Procedures that previously required the involvement of indigenous communities in decision-making have now been relaxed, and in many cases, even ignored altogether.

This raises widespread concern due to the increasing potential for marginalization of indigenous communities, particularly in the context of land acquisition by corporations through accelerated investment licensing schemes. Various civil society organizations and legal academics believe that this provision contradicts the spirit of the constitution, which recognizes and respects the rights of indigenous communities as stipulated in Article 18B paragraph (2) and Article 28I paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution. R. Haryo Pamungkas stated that this provision demonstrates the exclusive and pro-investment character of the law, which ignores the principles of social justice and the protection of the collective rights of indigenous communities. On the other hand, from a critical legal theory perspective, this policy reflects a power relationship between the state and corporations that instrumentalizes the law for the benefit of the market, not the people.

Therefore, the main legal problem facing indigenous peoples lies in the lack of a comprehensive national legal framework, reliance on regional administrative recognition, and the weak integration of indigenous law into the national legal system. The solution is to push for the immediate passage of the Indigenous Peoples Bill, which would provide a strong legal basis for the recognition, protection, and empowerment of indigenous peoples nationally and uniformly. This aligns with the principles of a democratic and pluralistic state based on the rule of law, as affirmed in the preamble to the 1945 Constitution, which states that the Indonesian state is based on law, not mere power.

Sociologically, indigenous communities play a crucial role in maintaining ecological and social balance in their environment. According to Piotr Sztompka in his book, "Sociology of Social Change," modernization and globalization have brought significant changes to the social and cultural structures of indigenous communities. Modernization often erodes local culture, leading to the loss of traditions and traditions. Indigenous communities have unique social systems and government structures, distinct from the typical village government system. Indigenous villages have their own governance procedures based on customary law and local wisdom passed down through generations. The social structure of indigenous communities typically consists of a customary chief, a customary council, and community members, each with their own roles and responsibilities in accordance with prevailing customs. This system enables indigenous communities to independently organize and manage their social, economic, and cultural lives.

In addition, indigenous communities also possess strong collective values, such as mutual cooperation, togetherness, and solidarity. These values are reflected in various social activities, such as traditional ceremonies, community service, and traditional celebrations. According to Clifford Geertz in *The Interpretation of Cultures*, these collective values play a crucial role in maintaining social cohesion and strengthening community identity. Social changes caused by modernization and globalization present particular challenges for sustaining indigenous communities. Many indigenous communities are marginalized and lose their land and natural resources due to development and exploitation of natural resources. This results in social disintegration and the loss of their cultural identity. According to Anthony Giddens in *Modernity and Self-Identity*, the process of modernization often causes drastic changes in

social and cultural structures, which can threaten the survival of deeply rooted traditional communities. (Beresaby, 2021) The marginalization of indigenous communities is often accompanied by social conflicts involving the government, companies, and indigenous communities. These conflicts typically relate to land and natural resource rights. In this case, indigenous communities lose their rights to their customary lands due to overlapping concessions for mining, plantations, or infrastructure projects. According to a report by AMAN (the Indigenous Peoples Alliance of the Archipelago), agrarian conflicts involving indigenous communities continue to increase annually, demonstrating that the rights of indigenous communities are still frequently ignored in development policies.

Based on the descriptions above, the author is interested in conducting research on the Existence of Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System in Indonesia. The problems in this research are related to the nature and existence of customary law communities, the regulation of the existence of customary law communities in the positive legal system and the role of the state in protecting the existence of customary law communities in Indonesia. The purpose of this research is to know and understand the nature of the existence of customary law communities, the regulation of the existence of customary law communities in the positive legal system and to find the role of the state in protecting the existence of customary law communities in Indonesia. Theoretically, this research can be useful as input for universities, especially the Faculty of Law, Social Sciences and Political Sciences Doctoral Program in order to conduct legal research, related to the Existence of Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System in Indonesia. Practically, this research is expected to be useful for contributing ideas to formulate legislation related to the Existence of Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System in Indonesia.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research utilizes normative legal research, which positions law as a system of norms. Each normative system relates to principles, norms, legal regulations, court decisions, agreements, and doctrines. According to Peter Mahmaud Marzuki, normative legal research is a process of discovering legal rules, legal principles, and legal doctrines that address the legal issues faced. (Yulianto and Mukti, 2010). In order to answer the problems in this research, the Philosophical Approach, the Statute Approach, the Conceptual Approach, and the Historical Approach were used. The types and sources of legal materials are in the form of Primary Legal Materials, Secondary Legal Materials, and Tertiary Legal Materials.

The legal material collection technique in this research was obtained through Library Research. The legal materials collected and obtained in the research were analyzed through legal interpretation and then processed deductively, namely drawing conclusions from a general problem to the specific problem faced. Then, the analysis was carried out using a qualitative method, namely the legal materials were presented in the form of a series of sentences that describe the results of the research based on the problem being studied. Accurately and comprehensively related to the Existence of Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System in Indonesia.

DISCUSSION

1. The Nature and Existence of Customary Legal Communities

Customary law communities are social entities that have long existed in the Indonesian archipelago before the formation of the modern Indonesian state. They have their own social structures, norms, and legal systems that are recognized and adhered to by their members. In a legal sense, a customary law community is defined as a group of people who live together in a social bond based on customs and have the ability to govern themselves, including in terms of communal ownership of property and certain territories. According to Soepomo, a customary law community is a form of legal community that has its own government and its own wealth based on the customary laws that exist within that community.

Customary law communities essentially have three main elements, namely: (1) a group of people who live together from generation to generation, (2) have legal ties based on applicable customary norms, and (3) have a certain area which is the basis of their social and economic life. (Praditha, 2023) These three elements form a social entity that possesses not only cultural uniqueness but also legal sovereignty derived from local traditions and wisdom. Hazairin stated that customary law communities are territorial societies that are collective and based on specific lineages that regulate their own affairs with their own customary laws.

From a sociological legal perspective, customary law communities reflect law as a social phenomenon that lives and develops within society. Eugen Ehrlich, in his theory of living law, emphasized that truly living law is the law that applies in social interactions, not merely the law written in statutes. This view is highly relevant in understanding the existence of customary law communities, which, although not always formalized in written state regulations, remain alive and are adhered to as law within their communities.

Within the framework of a state based on the rule of law, recognition of the existence of indigenous legal communities is a crucial part of ensuring justice and legal pluralism. Van Vollenhoven, a prominent figure in the study of customary law, stated that Indonesia has approximately 19 customary law regions (*rechtskringen*), each with its own distinct legal character. He emphasized that customary law is the original law of the Indonesian nation, rooted in the social realities of society and reflecting the nation's identity before the influence of colonial law. The essence of indigenous legal communities is also reflected in their ability to maintain collective values, deliberation, and balance with nature. (Duana et al. 2023) Koentjaraningrat explains that customary law communities possess a strong value system regarding kinship, social balance, and sacred relationships with their surroundings, which have implications for the norms and customary laws they adhere to. This demonstrates that customary law communities are not merely administrative or legal entities, but also comprehensive and integral systems of life.

In a constitutional context, recognition of customary law communities is stated in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution which states that "The State recognizes and respects customary law community units and their traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the

Republic of Indonesia." This formulation provides a strong legal basis for the existence of customary law communities, although its implementation still faces challenges in terms of inventory, official recognition, and adequate legal protection.

2. Arrangement Existence Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System

a. Constitutional Basis

The existence of customary law communities in Indonesia has been an integral part of the history and social life of society from the time of our ancestors to the present day. Customary law communities are defined as territorial or genealogical communities, possessing their own wealth, and distinguishable from other legal communities. They possess the capacity to act as an independent legal entity and govern themselves. The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia recognizes the existence of customary law communities as legal entities with their own characteristics, distinct from other legal subjects. Since the initial enactment of the 1945 Constitution, the explanatory section has mentioned the existence of "people's legal associations," referring to customary law communities that existed and developed long before Indonesian independence.(QIFTIAH, 2024).

As the largest archipelagic country in the world, Indonesia consists of more than 17,510 islands, with a sea area of approximately 5.8 million square kilometers and a coastline of 81,000 kilometers. Most of these islands are small, but contain a wealth of natural resources and environmental services that have the potential to support national economic growth. In the explanation of the 1945 Constitution, it is also stated that there are approximately 250 regions with original structures that are recognized as special areas. Examples include villages in the Javanese, Lombok and Bali regions, villages in Minangkabau, and hamlets and clans in the Palembang region and its surroundings. After the amendment to the 1945 Constitution, this explanation was removed, and the legal basis for indigenous peoples was placed in the Body of the 1945 Constitution. There are at least three main provisions in the 1945 Constitution that can form the basis for the existence and rights of indigenous peoples. As stated in Article 18B paragraph (2), Article 28I paragraph (3), and Article 32 paragraphs (1) and (2).

Table 1: Comparison of Settings Existence Public Customary Law in the Articles of the 1945 Constitution

Articles of the Constitution	Articles of the Constitution Comparison of Contents
Article 18B paragraph (2)	The state recognizes and respects the unity of customary law communities and their traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, which are regulated by law.
Article 28I paragraph (3)	The cultural identity and rights of traditional communities are respected in line with the development of the times and civilization.
Article 32 paragraphs (1) and (2)	Article (1): The state advances Indonesian national culture amidst world civilization by guaranteeing the freedom of society to maintain and develop its cultural values. Article (2): The state respects and maintains regional languages as national cultural treasures.

The existence and rights of indigenous legal communities in Indonesia are supported by several constitutional provisions that are most often referred to, namely Article 18B paragraph (2), Article 28I paragraph (3), and Article 32 paragraphs (1) and (2) of the 1945 Constitution. Although these provisions are the main basis, it does not mean that the rights of indigenous legal communities are only limited to these provisions. As part of Indonesian citizens, indigenous legal communities also have other constitutional rights such as the right to a decent living, a good environment, equality before the law, and other rights.

These three constitutional provisions differ in substance and approach to viewing indigenous communities. These differences are shown in the following table:

Table 2: Construction of Existence Arrangement And Rights of Indigenous Legal Communities in the 1945 Constitution

Regulation	Approach	Substance	State Responsibility	Restrictions / requirements
Article 18B verse (2)	Tata Government	1. Concerning the subject as a unit of customary law community, and 2. traditional rights of indigenous legal communities	The state recognizes and respects this. This is further regulated in law.	With the requirements as long as it lasts live, according to development society, in accordance with the principles of the State Unitary Republic Indonesia is regulated in Constitution
Article 28I verse (3)	Rights Man	1. Concerning cultural identity, and 2. Rights of traditional communities	Country Respect and protect	With the requirements in line with current development and civilization.
Article 32 Article (1) and verses (2)	Culture	1. Concerning the right to develop cultural values, and 2. Local language	Country respect and guarantee freedom	There isn't any

To date, discussions regarding indigenous peoples in the constitutional context have often focused on Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution. This is due to the provisions in that article which explicitly mention the term "indigenous legal communities." Meanwhile, Article 28I paragraph (3) uses the term "traditional communities," and Article 32 paragraphs (1) and (2) discuss "national culture," and "regional languages" which are indirectly related to indigenous peoples. These three constitutional provisions form the legal basis for the recognition and protection of the rights of indigenous peoples and have various normative implications in their implementation. Article 18B paragraph (2) emphasizes that the state recognizes and respects indigenous legal communities and their rights, as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Article 28I paragraph (3) provides guarantees for the cultural identity of traditional communities, which reflects the importance of protecting their existence in social dynamics. Meanwhile, Article 32 paragraphs (1) and (2) emphasize that the state must preserve national culture and regional languages while respecting regional cultural diversity, including indigenous cultures and regional languages.

One of the main challenges arises from the interpretation of the phrase "as long as it remains alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia" contained in the constitution. In development practice, this phrase is often interpreted to mean that the rights of indigenous peoples are only recognized as long as they do not conflict with the national development agenda. As a result, in many cases, the government tends to ignore or even diminish the traditional rights of indigenous peoples under the guise of development. Meanwhile, at the community level, there is a growing movement to defend and revitalize these rights.

b. Principles of Recognition and Protection in the Constitution

The provisions in Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia state that "The State recognizes and respects customary law communities and their traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, as regulated by law." This provision is not just an ordinary declarative norm, but rather reflects a principled framework that is rich in constitutional meaning and is fundamental to the relationship between the state and customary community entities in Indonesia. The first principle that is most prominent in this provision is the principle of recognition and respect. The phrase "recognize and respect" emphasizes that the state does not create customary law communities, but only affirms the existence of those who have lived historically and sociologically in society. Therefore, the nature of the recognition is declarative, not constitutive, meaning that the state only provides formal legitimacy to an existing existence.

According to Jimly Asshiddiqie, the principle of recognizing customary law communities in the Indonesian constitution is a form of formal legitimacy for customary communities that have existed in the history and culture of the Indonesian nation. (Thontowi, 2013) The state does not have the authority to create or eliminate the existence of these indigenous communities, but only provides formal recognition through the constitution and legislation as a form of declaration of sociological reality. Asshiddiqie stated that "this recognition is declarative, because indigenous legal communities are not institutions created by the state, but social entities that lived based on their own customary law before the birth of the Indonesian state."

In the context of legal philosophy, Hans Kelsen in his Grundnorm theory explains that the basic norm of a legal system is the initial agreement recognized by the community. In this case, customary law that lives in indigenous communities can become the basic norm (grundnorm) in their own communities, without having to rely on state legalization. Therefore, recognition by the state is only formalistic and administrative, without revoking the original authority of indigenous legal communities over their territory and governance. A similar point was also conveyed by Maria Farida Indrati, who explained that Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution contains the condition "as long as it is still alive" which aims to identify the actual existence of indigenous legal communities, but does not question their origins or historical legality. Therefore, the state's actions to regulate indigenous legal communities in legislation are not aimed at creating their existence, but to adjust administrative procedures and legal protection to communities that already exist in social reality.

This declarative nature has important legal consequences. First, state recognition is not an absolute requirement for the existence of indigenous legal communities; that is, even if not yet recognized in formal legal documents, indigenous legal communities still possess sociological and legal legitimacy within their own communities. Second, this declarative recognition provides a basis for protecting traditional rights, such as customary land, customary leadership systems, and local wisdom, even if they have not yet been fully legalized by law. Third, the state is obliged to prove that indigenous legal communities still exist empirically, but may not use regulatory limitations as an excuse to deny their existence.

The second principle, actuality or factual validity (principle of actuality/living law), is reflected in the phrase "as long as they are still alive." This requirement implies that not all entities once considered indigenous communities are automatically recognized by the state, but only those that still exist in real terms and have value systems, customary legal institutions, and social structures that are still practiced and recognized by their members. Thus, the state is only obliged to recognize indigenous communities that actually live in contemporary social reality, not merely based on historical claims. In line with this, there is the principle of dynamism and societal development. Customary law and the social systems of indigenous communities are not static entities, but continue to develop and adapt to changes in society, technology, and global norms. Therefore, even if recognition is granted, the development of indigenous communities must remain based on the values of human rights, gender equality, and the public interest, to ensure that customs do not become a shield for discriminatory or exclusionary practices.

The third principle is the principle of conformity with the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). In this case, the existence and autonomy of indigenous legal communities must not conflict with the constitution, Pancasila, national integrity, or the national legal system. This means that customs that fundamentally conflict with the principles of the unitary state or the rule of law cannot be used as grounds for demanding absolute recognition. This principle establishes a boundary that emphasizes that cultural autonomy must be subject to broader national interests.

The fourth principle, the principle of formal legality, is as stipulated in the phrase "as regulated by law." This means that recognition of indigenous legal communities is not simply based on the constitution, but requires technical regulation through legislation, for example, through the Village, Forestry, or Land Laws. This principle is crucial for ensuring legal certainty, clarity of procedures for identifying and verifying indigenous legal communities, and standards for protecting their traditional rights.

3. Constitutional Recognition and Respect for Indigenous Legal Communities

Recognition and respect for indigenous legal communities (MHA) is an integral part of the formation of a national legal system that is just and rooted in local values. The Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia expressly provides a place for the existence of indigenous legal communities within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution stipulates that "The State recognizes and

respects the units of indigenous legal communities and their traditional rights as long as they are still alive and in accordance with the development of society and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia." This provision contains the meaning that the state not only recognizes the existence of indigenous legal communities formally, but is also obliged to guarantee their existence, sustainability, and rights in various aspects of life.

According to Maria Farida Indrati, the phrase "as long as it is alive and in accordance with societal developments and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia" should be understood as an effort to maintain a balance between recognizing customs and the needs of modernization and national integration. The state cannot ignore the existence of customary social and legal systems that existed long before Indonesia's independence. However, such recognition is not absolute; it must be within constitutional boundaries.

Therefore, there are inherent requirements, namely that MHA must exist in real terms and have a functional social structure. Jimly Asshiddiqie emphasized that constitutional recognition of customary law communities is a manifestation of the principle of legal pluralism within the framework of a state based on the rule of law. In his book, *The Constitution and Indonesian Constitutionalism*, he states that legal pluralism is a crucial prerequisite for realizing substantial democracy because it respects the diversity of value systems and norms within society. This demonstrates that customary law is not an alien entity within the Indonesian legal system, but rather a living source of law with social and historical legitimacy.

From a legal theory perspective, the existence of MHA can also be analyzed through a responsive legal approach. According to Philippe Nonet and Philip Selznick, responsive law is law that is sensitive to social aspirations and able to accommodate cultural diversity and social dynamics within society. Therefore, the recognition of indigenous legal communities is not only a form of cultural preservation, but also a state strategy in responding to the legal needs of the community in a more contextual and equitable manner.

According to Mochtar Kusumaatmadja, in his theory of "law as a means of societal renewal," the Indonesian legal system must be open to local values and customs that exist within the community. This means that constitutional recognition of MHA is not an obstacle to the development of national law, but rather an opportunity to build more inclusive, reflective, and contextual laws. He stated that law cannot be separated from the culture of the society that gave birth to it, so customary law can be used as an instrument in the development of national law as long as it is in line with the values of social justice.

In state practice, constitutional recognition of indigenous legal communities also reflects the basic values of human rights. Article 28I paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution states that "The cultural identity and rights of traditional communities are respected in accordance with the development of the times and civilization." This provision emphasizes that recognition of MHA rights is not only part of social justice, but also an inherent human right. According to Yance Arizona, this provision reinforces the constitutional guarantee that the state not only passively recognizes, but also actively protects and empowers indigenous communities. However, the implementation of constitutional recognition of MHA does not always run smoothly.

Many cases show that MHA rights, especially those related to land rights, natural resources, and management of customary territories, are often ignored in development practices. This indicates a gap between constitutional norms and regulatory implementation at the level of laws and technical policies. In this context, Boedi Harsono emphasized the importance of harmonizing national law and customary law to prevent overlapping or marginalization of indigenous communities.

Legally, recognition of MHA has also been outlined in various laws and regulations, such as Law Number 5 of 1960 concerning Basic Agrarian Regulations (UUPA), which states that customary rights and similar rights of indigenous peoples are recognized as long as they exist in reality. This provision strengthens the existence of customary law in the agrarian realm. However, as criticized by Prof. M. Daud Silalahi, this conditional recognition often creates loopholes for regional and central governments to delay recognition of MHA based on the interpretation of "as long as they exist in reality."

Therefore, clear and consistent parameters are needed to determine the existence of MHA. In a global context, recognition of indigenous peoples' rights is also recognized through the 2007 United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), which was adopted by Indonesia. This declaration recognizes the rights of indigenous peoples to autonomy, cultural identity, language, customary law, and rights to their land and natural resources. Although this declaration is not legally binding, its principles serve as a benchmark for international standards that can encourage national legal reforms to better support indigenous peoples.

Satjipto Rahardjo's academic perspective also deserves attention. Within the framework of "progressive law," he asserts that law should not stop at formal texts but must strive for substantive justice. Therefore, in the context of indigenous legal communities, formal constitutional recognition must be accompanied by concrete measures in the form of protection, empowerment, and access to resources that are essential to the identity and survival of indigenous communities. Satjipto even believes that if state law fails to recognize and protect customary law, what will occur is repression of the existence of local values and a new form of colonialism disguised as formal legality. Within the framework of legal philosophy, Hans Kelsen's view that the legal system is a hierarchy of norms (Stufenbau Theory) can be used to explain the position of customary law within the Indonesian legal system. Customary law, to the extent that it is recognized and does not conflict with norms above it (namely the 1945 Constitution), can have legally binding force. This means that, as long as there is explicit recognition in the constitution and national law, the validity of customary law has a legitimate normative basis within the Indonesian positive legal system.

However, the biggest challenge currently lies in institutional matters. As Hikmahanto Juwana noted, weaknesses in data collection, verification, and legalization of indigenous communities have led to inconsistencies in legal enforcement. Many regions lack regional regulations (Perda) on the recognition of MHA, and even if they do exist, they are often not supported by adequate budgets and institutions. This reflects a weak political will to implement the constitutional mandate. Constitutional recognition of MHA also has implications for regional

governance, particularly since the enactment of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages. This law explicitly recognizes "Customary Villages" as entities with their own structures, territories, and laws. According to I Gde Pudja, this represents a significant leap in efforts to institutionalize indigenous communities within formal government structures, a gap that has often been overlooked. However, this recognition must be accompanied by mechanisms that do not standardize customs but allow them to live according to their own identity.

From a sociological perspective, the existence of indigenous legal communities is closely linked to local identity, spirituality, and cosmology. Therefore, as Koentjaraningrat stated, recognition of indigenous peoples is not merely a formal legal matter, but also touches on the cultural and historical aspects inherent in the lives of these communities. If the state fails to provide a fair living space for indigenous peoples, cultural decay and social alienation will occur, leading to horizontal and vertical conflict.

Therefore, constitutional recognition and respect for indigenous legal communities must not stop at the level of normative rhetoric. There must be political sincerity, legal courage, and administrative firmness in recognizing the existence, granting rights, and involving indigenous peoples in national development. In the spirit of legal pluralism and social justice, the state is obliged to make customary law a crucial pillar in building a just and inclusive national legal system.

For the empowerment of indigenous communities to be effective, it is necessary to establish an independent state institution specifically tasked with handling indigenous peoples' affairs, as proposed in the Indigenous Peoples Bill. This institution must have the authority to verify, mediate conflicts, and advocate for indigenous peoples' rights. Furthermore, empowerment must also be based on the principle of free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC), as stipulated in the 2007 UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. Empowering indigenous communities is not only a development strategy but also part of the legal democratization process. This requires a transformation in how the state views customary law, from subordination to recognition, from exclusion to inclusion. As Boaventura de Sousa Santos argues, local law must be seen as an "epistemology from the South" that contributes to the formation of global justice.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

a. The Nature and Existence of Customary Legal Communities

Based on the results of the studies conducted, it can be concluded that the essence of customary law communities lies in their existence as social and legal entities born from a long history of human interaction with their environment, and passed down through generations through a unique system of values, norms, and customary institutions. Customary law communities are not merely traditional communities, but are collective legal entities with their own systems of governance, customary territories, and effective dispute resolution mechanisms within their communities.

b. Regulation of the Existence of Customary Law Communities in the Positive Legal System

Regulations regarding indigenous legal communities are not only enshrined in the constitution, but also in various sectoral laws and regulations, such as Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, Law No. 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management, and Law No. 5 of 1960 concerning Basic Agrarian Regulations (UUPA). This shows that the state not only recognizes the existence of indigenous legal communities as socio-cultural entities, but also as legal subjects capable of carrying out government functions. However, the existence of these regulations has not been followed by a systematic implementation system and mechanism to establish indigenous legal communities in an inclusive and accommodating manner.

c. The Role of the State in Protecting the Existence of Indigenous Legal Communities in Indonesia

Protecting indigenous communities is not only a moral and political obligation, but also a legal obligation stemming from the 1945 Constitution (UUD 1945), various national legal instruments, and international conventions ratified by Indonesia. The ideal role of the state does not merely rest on normative recognition, but must be translated into concrete policies that guarantee customary land rights, local wisdom, access to natural resources, and the political participation of indigenous communities in decision-making processes affecting their lives.

2. Suggestions

The state needs to immediately ratify the Draft Law on Indigenous Peoples (RUU MHA) as the primary legal umbrella that is comprehensive, explicit, and binding in regulating the status, rights, obligations, territories, and institutions of indigenous peoples. The government must synchronize and harmonize overlapping and contradictory sectoral laws and regulations regarding the existence of indigenous peoples, such as conflicts between the Forestry Law, the Mineral and Coal Law, the Land Law, and the Environmental Law, which often serve as the legal basis for ignoring indigenous peoples' customary rights. The state must encourage the strengthening of the institutional capacity of indigenous peoples, both through legal education, regional management training, and economic facilitation based on local potential. This strengthening aims to ensure that indigenous peoples are not only objects of law, but also active actors in equitable and sustainable development.

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